

The Effects of the Parent Training Program for Obesity Reduction on Health Behaviors of School-Age Children

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Abstract : The purposes of the study were to evaluate the effectiveness of the Parent Training Program for Obesity Reduction (PTPOR) on health behaviors of school-age children. An Ecological Systems Theory (EST) was approached the study and a randomized control trial was used in this study. Participants were school-age overweight or obese children and their parents. One hundred and one parent-child dyads were recruited and random assigned into the PTPOR (N=30), Educational Intervention or EI (N=32), and control group (N=39). The parents in the PTPOR group participated in five sessions including an educational session, a cooking session, aerobic exercise training, 2-time group discussion sessions, and 4-time telephoned counseling sessions. Repeated Measure ANCOVA was used to analyze data. The results presented that the outcomes of the PTPOR group were better than the EI and the control groups at 1st, 8th, and 32nd weeks after finishing the program such as child exercise behavior ($F(2,97) = 3.98, p = .02$) and child dietary behavior ($F(2,97) = 9.42, p = .00$). The results suggest that nurses and health care providers should utilize the PTPOR for child weight reduction and for the health promotion of a lifestyle among overweight and obese children.

Keywords : parent training program, obesity reduction, child health behaviors, school-age children

Conference Title : ICBPS 2014 : International Conference on Behavioral and Psychological Sciences

Conference Location : London, United Kingdom

Conference Dates : May 26-27, 2014